

Spectral studies of complexation reaction between copper(II) and 2,3,4-trihydroxyphenylethylidene benzoic acid hydrazide

S. Paul Douglas^a, S. Sri Hari^b and P. Nageswara Rao^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Warangal-506 004, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009, India

Manuscript received 11 May 1999, accepted 20 May 1999

The complex of Cu^{II} with 2,3,4-trihydroxyphenylethylidene benzoic acid hydrazide has been prepared and characterised by physical and spectral data.

2,3,4-Trihydroxyphenylethanone (Gallacetophenone) and its oxime, hydrazone, semicarbazone and thiosemicarbazone derivatives have been employed as analytical reagents for the gravimetric, amperometric and spectrophotometric determination of various metal ions¹. It is also known that hydrazones of various carbonyl compounds act as multidentate ligands with transition metals forming coloured chelates². In the present note 2,3,4-trihydroxyphenylethylidene benzoic acid hydrazide (gallacetophenone benzoylhydrazide) (TPBH) and its Cu^{II} complex have been prepared.

TPBH

Results and Discussion

The ligand is a crystalline solid and is stable at room temperature. Analytical data of the Cu^{II} complex show 1 : 2 metal : ligand stoichiometry.

The Cu^{II} complex in its thermogram showed a weight-loss in the temperature range of 260–465°, the final product above 465° corresponding to CuO. Further, the weight-loss reveals a break at 295° which corresponds to one ligand molecule. Subsequently, the second ligand molecule got lost at 295–465° with CuO as the final product. Thus, the analysis of thermogram gives further support to the composition of the complex on the basis of elemental analysis data.

The bonding sites of the ligand have been inferred by comparing its infrared spectrum with that of the complex. The IR ligand band at 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N) underwent a nega-

tive shift by about 40 cm⁻¹ in the complex indicating coordination of the nitrogen of this group³. The ligand band at 3000 cm⁻¹ (hydrogen bonded OH)⁴ showed up in the complex at 3200 cm⁻¹ with a reduced intensity suggesting that the deprotonation of the *o*-hydroxy group has taken place. The ν_{N-H} appeared as a sharp band at 3350 cm⁻¹ in both the ligand and the complex⁴. The $\nu_{C=O}$ ligand band (1670 cm⁻¹) position remained unaltered in the complex, ruling out coordination through oxygen of this group⁵. The coordination of copper through nitrogen of azomethine group and oxygen of *o*-hydroxy group of the ligand is further substantiated by the appearance, in the complex, of non-ligand bands at 470 (M–N) and 520 cm⁻¹ (M–O). Thus it may be concluded that the ligand acts as a mononegative, bidentate one coordinating through oxygen of *o*-hydroxy group and nitrogen of azomethine group.

The electronic spectrum of the complex showed two peaks at 13350 and 18980 cm⁻¹ assignable respectively to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions of square-planar geometry⁶.

The ESR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex is anisotropic in nature and shows two peak envelopes, one of small intensity towards low field and the other of large intensity towards high field. Each of these envelopes is resolved into four peaks due to hyperfine splitting by copper nucleus and the various parameters calculated from the spectrum using appropriate equations are as follows : g_{\parallel} , 2.25; g_{\perp} , 2.05; g_{av} , 2.12; A_{\parallel} , 167×10^4 cm⁻¹; A_{\perp} , 54×10^4 cm⁻¹; A_{qv} , 92×10^4 cm⁻¹; α^2 , 0.87; β^2 , 0.56; γ^2 , 0.62; $-\lambda$, 413 cm⁻¹. A comparison of the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} indicates that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ and so the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the metal $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital with B_{1g} ground state⁷. The α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 , the respective measures of an in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding and out-of-plane π -bonding suggest moderate/appreciable in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding and out-

of-plane π -bonding⁸. Further, the spin-orbit coupling constant of Cu^{II} ion in the complex ($\lambda = -413 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is lower than the free-ion value ($\lambda_0 = -828 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), indicating considerable mixing of ground and excited terms.

On the basis of the foregoing data, square-planar structure has been proposed for the complex.

Experimental

2,3,4-Trihydroxyphenylethylidene benzoic acid hydrazide was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 2,3,4-hydroxyphenylethanone (8.4 g) and benzoic acid hydrazide (6.8 g) in ethanol for 8 h on a water-bath and the solid that separated on cooling was crystallized from ethanol and vacuum dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 (12 g, 80%), m.p. 214° (Found: C, 62.93; H, 4.92, N, 9.79; O, 22.36. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 62.97; H, 4.87; N, 9.73; O, 22.38%); m/z 286 (M^+ , 60), 273 (10), 257 (4), 228 (3), 164 (8), 152 (3), 144 (2), 137 (3), 122 (3), 107 (25), 105 (100), 94 (2), 78 (80), 44 (50%).

The Cu^{II} complex was prepared by mixing $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in water with the ethanolic solution of TPBH in 1 : 2 molar ratio and refluxing the mixture on a water-bath for 1 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to half of its volume, cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The C, H, N and O analyses were done on a Carlo-Erba EA 1108 analyzer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8201 PC spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (ethanol) on a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a HP MS EM-5989A instrument

(70 eV) and ESR spectra (DMF) at LNT on a Varian-E4 spectrometer. Thermogram was recorded employing a Seiko TG/DTA-32 instrument.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Chennai, for providing the ESR spectrum, to Head, U.S.I.C., Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, for thermal analysis, to the authorities of I.I.C.T., Hyderabad, and to Principal, R.E.C., Warangal, for facilities.

References

1. K. A. Reddy and Y. K. Reddy, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1971, **74**, 159; K. A. Reddy, Ph.D. Thesis, S. V. University, Tirupati, 1973; P. N. Rao and K. A. Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 402; P. N. Rao, Ph.D. Thesis Kakatiya University, Warangal, 1982; K. R. Reddy, Ph.D. Thesis, Kakatiya University, Warangal, 1984; K. R. Reddy, P. N. Rao and K. A. Reddy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **54**, 422.
2. M. Katyal and W. A. E. McBryde, 'Analytical Aspects of Hydrazones', *Technical News Service, Baroda*, 1978, **10**, 22.
3. R. L. Dutta and A. K. Sarkar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 57.
4. R. S. Drago, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi, 1996.
5. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978.
6. B. C. Warden, E. Billing and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 78.
7. R. L. Dutta and A. Syamal, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", 2nd ed., Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi, 223.
8. S. G. Kulkarni, D. V. Jahagirdar and D. D. Khanolkar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 251.